

SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL ANALYSIS AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE SPIRITUAL AND MORAL VIEWS OF ALISHER NAVOI IN THE NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: This article provides a philosophical analysis of the spiritual and moral views of The Thinker Alisher Navoi. The socio-philosophical significance of spirituality and morality in the creation of the foundation of a new Uzbekistan is highlighted. The poetic verses of Alisher Navoi have been philosophically analyzed.

Keywords: Renaissance, spirituality, morality, faith, unity, gyneal, culture, religion, heritage, idea.

We live in the development of time and in the period of renewal of worldviews. The heritage of The Thinker Alisher Navoi, the secular and religious significance of spiritual and moral guises are growing today. "it is no secret that in today's global space, the role and importance of the upbringing of the younger generation in the current conditions, when mutual competition, various political, economic, ideological contradictions are incredibly intensified, is growing more than ever" [1,292]. Present: in the Prevention of aggression against each other instead of living peacefully among themselves; in cases where each country has to solve its problem, a person can not help a person, it is necessary to turn into a call of faith, when, due to the effects of globalization, hundreds of children of which one people walk in other countries; even in the era of slavery, in seeking and finding answers to such problems in cases where he is going out on street protests, saying that the chief, elected by him, should leave the throne, Navoi's genial works will be able to actively come to the aid of the 21st century. His ideas about the Righteous King are a sign that Navoi, at his own expense, built the madrasas "Ixlosiya" and "Nizomiya", the medical hospital "Shifoiya" (hospital), dozens of bridges, rabbis, supplied hundreds of Taliban of Science with food, clothing. "The fact that Husayn Boyqaro took it upon himself to be a retainer to the with Navoi is a sign of how great a spiritual he was, that he highly valued literature, art, creation. But it is necessary to note that the action of Husayn Boyqaro shows not only what kind of King and man he was, he also testifies to the height of the moral of society, to the fact that Kings can correctly accept and adequately assess their behavior, similar to the above. The fact that the head of state himself was engaged in creativity, sought enlightenment,

sponsored the people of creativity was an example and imitation of the nobility” [2,71]. Alisher Navoi's friendship with Husayn Boyqaro, his dignity and the extraordinary and beautiful results of this closeness are still worth the admiration of world-class Kings and poets.

We think that the lofty philosophical theme of the essence of Man and living in “Hayrat ul-abror”, the beautiful artistic solutions to the pain problems of his time, can apply to our time.

Alisher Navoi's intellectual legacy extends beyond the perspective of his poetry and moral point, and covers a deep commitment to humanity embodied in contemporary debates about cultural diversity, tolerance, and intercultural dialogue.

Navoi's humanistic perspective is reflected in his poetry in the focus on universal experiences and emotions. Whether it expresses love, longing or moral principles, its verses resonate with readers of different cultural and religious backgrounds.

His commitment to humanism reinforces the idea that all human beings have common aspirations, expectations, and moral ideals. Alisher Navoi's legacy of tolerance and humanity continues the contemporary debate on multiculturalism and intercultural dialogue. Its recognition of the importance of cultural exchange and its promotion of understanding and respect among different communities remains relevant in a globalized world characterized by increased cultural and religious diversity.

Alisher Navoi's contribution to humanism extends beyond his literary and moral works, and covers a holistic worldview that celebrates cultural diversity, interfaith dialogue, and the generality of all. His focus on the interdependence of human experiences, his promotion of cultural exchange, his promotion of tolerance and understanding make Navoi an eternal , whose humanitarian values continue to inspire and guide us towards a more harmonious and inclusive world. "Alisher Navoi, in his “Khamisa”, argues that a delightful attitude to labor in young people is a natural need. Because as a result of this work, a person achieves his goals in his life and strives for the richness of his labors. The process associated with a delightful approach to Labor about the help of Farhad to the canal diggers in his epic” Farhad and Shirin " is considered the criterion and social factor for the education of young people in an aesthetic spirit. Alisher Navoi, on the example of Farhad, described in artistic form the need to harmonize the physical and mental abilities of young people with Labor, and the fact that Labor is the basis of all wealth [3,94].

Alisher Navoi's moral and humanistic views, which stemmed from the cultural and intellectual environment of the Timurid period, resonated in modern society, providing valuable insights and guidance in a world characterized by complex moral problems, cultural diversity and global interdependence. His legacy continues through the continued relevance of his moral foundations, the promotion of cultural exchange, and the emphasis on universal values.

Navoi's attention to the moral dimension of language and the influence of linguistic choice on morality is of urgent importance in debates related to political correctness, hate speech and the role of language in the formation of social values. In the digital age, where communication is ubiquitous, Navoi's recognition of the responsibility associated with the use of words provides a valuable perspective for individuals and societies seeking to foster respectful and ethical discourse.

Navoi's promotion of cultural exchange and tolerance serves as a model for solving his problems in modern society. In a time of globalization where people from different cultural backgrounds interact daily, Navoi's commitment to cultural pluralism and promotion of understanding and respect among cultures and beliefs provides a plan for building inclusive and harmonious communities. Alisher Navoi calls on different el-yurt to live in harmony and harmony. He calls on humanity to unity as the differential of One Planet Earth, focusing not on the qualities that separate peoples, but on the qualities that carry them close together, equal.

Navoi's humanistic values and belief in the general humanity of all people are especially relevant in a world characterized by global problems such as climate change, poverty, political conflicts. His views on humanity emphasize the importance of empathy, compassion and cooperation between peoples and cultures in addressing pressing global issues and promoting peace and harmony.

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